

effects. The only exception was for those determining the related characters of tiller and panicle number, which also displayed some epistasis of the additive \times dominance type. On the other hand, the genetical architecture of the characters in cross 2 was more complex. With the exception of days to maturity and tiller number, all were controlled by genes that, in addition to displaying additive and dominance effects, also displayed epistatic effects, predominantly of the duplicate type.

Predictions of the proportion of recombinant inbred lines, the means of which meet the desired new plant type targets, can be extracted by single seed

descent from these crosses. Based on information obtained from F_3 families, this should be easy to achieve in both crosses for days to heading, days to maturity, tiller number, culm length, and panicle number. It will be less easy to achieve for spikelet number, doubtful to achieve for proportion of filled spikelets and harvest index, and very unlikely for grain yield in either cross.

The pattern of genetic correlations between characters, in cross 1 estimated from F_3 data, was very different from that in cross 2. Thus, while in cross 1 grain yield was moderately correlated ($r = 0.56$) only to days to heading, in cross 2 it was highly correlated ($r = 0.75$) to dry matter, tiller and

panicle number, panicle length, and spikelet number. This indicates that the chief cause of these correlations is the linkage disequilibrium of linked genes, rather than pleiotropy. This, in turn, suggests that it should be possible to extract inbred lines from appropriate crosses achieving the desired multiple new plant type.

Results suggest, however, that the targets for proportion of filled spikelets, for harvest index and, in particular, for grain yield will be achieved only after several cycles of inbreeding, each of which is initiated by crossing the best inbred lines from the previous cycle. ■

Molecular basis of heterosis in hybrid rice and hybrid maize revealed by mRNA amplification

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We have detected the mRNA subpopulations derived from hybrid rice, hybrid maize, and their parental lines by differential display. Messenger RNA amplification reveals that profound alteration of gene expression occurs in the hybrid genetic background when compared with parental lines. Regulation of gene expression in the hybrid environment includes enhancement, selective transcription, silencing, cosuppression, and activity of specific genes that are silencing in parental lines. Comparing gene expression patterns in hybrids with those in parental lines provides the underlying information to analyze the biological processes controlling heterosis formation.

To investigate the relationship between gene expression regulation and heterosis, we tried to use a differential display method to detect gene products from hybrid rice, hybrid maize, and their parental lines. Rice F_1 hybrids were from a cross between

two indica lines, Zhangsha 97 and Minfei 63, and maize F_1 hybrids were from a cross between two inbred cultivars, YD4 and H24. The total mRNAs of the leaves of seedlings of hybrid rice, hybrid maize, and their parental lines were isolated using the method of Liang (1993). Two anchored oligo-dT primers, 3'-T11CA and 3'-T11GC, were used to reverse-transcribe the mRNA subpopulation. Two short arbitrary primers, 5-L1(5'-GATCGCATTG-3') and 5'-L2(5'-TACAACGAGG-3'), were designed to make paired primer sets and to amplify cDNA subpopulations. Amplified labeling cDNAs were separated on sequencing gel. In side-by-side comparison, significant changes of the mRNA constitution and quantity appeared in hybrid rice and hybrid maize.

Six kinds of gene expression alteration in the hybrids were detected based on amplified cDNA patterns: some new mRNAs that are absent in parental lines appear in hybrid seedlings, meaning these genes are transcribed only in hybrids; maternal genes become inactive in hybrids; paternal genes are silencing in hybrids; allelic genes of two parental lines show cosuppression in hybrids; some genes are overexpressed in hybrids when compared with their expression in parental lines; and some genes are underexpressed in hybrids. We also found many genes expressed

normally in hybrids. We therefore conclude that in the hybrid genetic background, gene expression is altered in a variety of ways.

It was reported recently that the major genetic basis of heterosis in rice is dominance as revealed by QTL analysis using molecular markers. In contrast, it seems that the prominent factors contributing heterosis in maize is overdominance (Stuber et al 1992, Xiao et al 1995). Further studies of gene expression alternation in hybrids will provide important information about the molecular basis of overdominance and dominance in heterosis.

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